

Machine Learning in Sales Prediction

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Abstract— Machine learning is an area of research focused on comprehending and developing "learning" processes, or processes that use data to enhance performance on a given set of tasks. These days, sales prediction (forecasting) involves training a model to gather sales activity data, learn how each input contributes to a weighted output, and use the model to predict outcomes based on previously unknown and real-time performance data. The purpose of this study is to suggest a factor for forecasting Walmart Companies' future sales while taking account of those from prior years. With the use of machine learning models such as Decision Tree, Random Forest, and XGBoost Regressor. A thorough investigation of sales prediction is conducted. The calculation takes into account data characteristics including weekly sales, different store departments, and types of store holidays.

Keywords—Decision Tree, Random Forest, XGB Boost Regressor

I. INTRODUCTION

Algorithms for machine learning play a crucial role in revenue forecasting. The estimation of weekly, monthly, quarterly, and annual sales totals frequently uses historical data, market trends, and the state of the current sales pipeline as benchmarks. Without accurate forecasting, a company may overspend and lose margin or underspend and underperform on sales. Depending on your estimate for potential sales in the upcoming months or quarters, forecasting can aid sales teams in achieving success.

Sales projections assist companies in making more informed decisions based on anticipated revenue, which will enable them to:

- Predict the expected profit (or loss) for the specified period.
- Plan for HR and organize staffing levels.
- Create a manufacturing schedule that will allow you to meet demand.
- Grants authority to sales leaders.

II. RELATED WORKS

Purvika et. al[1] This research, proposes a factor for estimating Big Mart companies' upcoming sales while taking their historical sales into consideration. utilizing many machine learning techniques. The forecast includes various data.

Nikitha et. al[2] In order to forecast the sales of various products and comprehend the influences of various elements on the sales of the products, the instance of Big Mart, a one-stop shopping center, has been examined in this paper. examining several elements of a dataset gathered for Big Mart and the process used to create a predictive model including machine learning models like Linear Regression and Random Forest.

Xian et. al[3] To complete basket analysis and make product recommendations based on the findings, the association rules theory, the Apriori algorithm, and the product recommendation model are all used. To create prediction models, the study paper blends XGBoost and Random Forest machine learning techniques. For enhancing sales also a market response, the suggested recommendation model offers solid recommendation outcomes and sales combinations.

Naveenraj et. al[4]In this study, sales forecasting for big-box stores is done using experimental machine-learning techniques. In-depth studies of sales prediction use machine learning models including Linear Ridge and Lasso Regression Models, Random Forest, Gradient Boosted Decision Tree, AdaBoost Regressor, Xgboost, and Light Gradient Boosting Machine.

Yasaman et. al[5] This study aims to offer accurate results for anticipating time ahead sales needs of a firm by using methods such as the Triple Exponential Smoothing, and with Seasonal Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average for traditional time-series forecasting.

III. DATA VISUALIZATION

A. Heat map used to find a correlation between the dataset attributes

Here, the association between the target variable and the other qualities is shown using a heat map, a color-encoded matrix from the Seaborn data visualisation toolkit.

The less dependent the target variable is on a certain attribute, the higher the intensity of that attribute's colour is in relation to the target variable.

B. Count Plots

B.1 The distribution of different types of stores in the data set. Such as A, B, and C. Through the different types of stores find out which store has more sales.

B.2 The count plot for different items is sold in different departments. Here taking almost fifteen different kinds of items. It observed which items are selling the most.

B.3 Count Plot describes the different store sales according to the weekly sales. This count plot showcases which store produces more sales.

B.4 This count plot for various departments in a store to find out the departments produce the most sales.

B.4 Showcasing yearly sales according to the weekly sales

IV. DATA PROCESSING

Processing of data done in the manual way it will be difficult. Various Machine learning algorithm help in a way to process the data in an easy manner. Before deciding whether to use the information or not, preprocessing aims to determine what kind of information is required. For pre-processing, clean, well prepared

data is crucial. Here, the activities that make up data processing include:

- A. Taking in the dataset: Here, I am taking a dataset of stores to check future sales and importing the data set in the .csv file format.
- B. cleansing process :Some columns that don't help the algorithm reach its conclusions must be deleted as part of the data cleansing process. Here are the dropped attributes:
Temperature, Fuel_Price, Unemployment, MarkDown1, MarkDown2, MarkDown3, MarkDown4, MarkDown5
- C. Dealing with missing values: Missing values must be handled carefully to ensure that there is no discrepancy in the data that will be put into the model. In this case, the CPI had some missing figures. The mean of every other entry in the column is used to fill in the empty spaces in the case of CPI.
- D. Convert attribute information: In order to maximize the benefits of machine learning principles, which is using mathematical models to address problems, First need to make sure that we have enough numerical data. Importing the Sklearn library to taking the functions "IsHoliday," "Type," and "item".
- E. Separating variables that are independent and dependent: The dependencies are the results that must be ultimately assessed and then contrasted with one another. The features or input factors known as independent variables cannot be altered in any way, and as a result, the objectives are predicted. Independent variables include: 'Dept', 'item', 'CPI', and 'year'. Dependent variables include: 'Size ', 'Weekly_sales ', 'Type ', 'Store ', 'IsHoliday', 'week', 'month',
- F. Splitting the dataset into a test and training set: preventing the overfit, the train and test sets are not imported as two different datasets. Thus, splitting is carried out within a single dataset. We must train the model using the training dataset. Datasets for tests are those that can be used to forecast test results..

V. ALGORITHMS USED

A. Decision Tree Algorithm

The root node is the first to be taken into account in a top-down method, and it is a straightforward model with little bias that may be utilized to generate a classifier model. It is a well-known artificial intelligence model. a selection Tree is a supervised learning method that may be applied to classification and regression issues, however, it is most frequently chosen to address classification issues. It is a tree-structured classifier, where internal nodes stand in for a dataset's features, branches for the decision-making process, and each leaf node for the classification result. It is a strong method for multi-variable analysis and a strong approach to data mining. This method illustrates the factors that go into achieving a specific objective, as well as the reasons for achieving the goal and the methods used to carry it out, in a number of contexts.

B. Random Forest Regressor

The bagging method makes use of a collection of decision trees to help it produce accurate results. Boosting and bagging are two of the most common ensemble algorithms that try to overcome higher variability and higher prejudice. For bagging, base

models make use of a variety of random samplings of records from the training dataset. The distribution of samples from the main data file using row sampling and feature sampling with replacement procedures for each of the decision trees; decision trees tend to overfit, resulting in high training accuracy but low real accuracy when used to their full depth. Bootstrapping is the name of this approach. Each model was trained using all of these data sets, and whenever test data is given to a trained model that is already in use, the predictions made by each model are combined to produce an outcome that is the average of all the generated results. In this case, a process known as aggregation is used to combine the various findings. The hyperparameter that this algorithm needs to control is the number of decision trees that must be considered when developing a model.

- [4] Naveenraj R, Vinayaga Sudharam R.” Prediction of Big Mart Sales Using Machine Learning”.[2021]
- [5] Yasaman Ensafi, Saman Hassanzadeh Amin, Guoqing Zhang, Bharat Shah.” Time-series forecasting of seasonal items sales using machine learning-A Comparative analysis”.[2022]

C. XGBoost Regressor

Extreme Gradient Boosting, commonly known as XGBoost, has been used to create an efficient model with high computing speed and efficacy. The formula uses the ensemble approach to produce predictions in order to improve previous forecasts. This method mimics expected errors from some decision trees. The creation of this model also documents the significance of the contributions made by each feature to the forecasting of the overall construction performance score. This feature value shows the impact each attribute has on predicting school achievement in absolute terms. By building decision trees concurrently, XGBoost aids in parallelization. This algorithm can evaluate any huge and complex model, which makes distributed computing another important characteristic it possesses. Due to the vast and diverse datasets it analyses, it is an out-core computation. This calculative model does a good job of handling resource usage. To lower the error, an additional model must be used at each phase.

VI. RESULTS

The sales of several Walmart stores have been predicted using machine learning methods like Decision Tree, XGBoost, and Random Forest. Several factors, including training and testing accuracies, Mean Squared Error (MSE), and Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), are determined. Random Forest Algorithm is found to be the most suitable.

CONCLUSION

Machine learning approaches prove to be a crucial feature for designing business plans while taking into consideration consumer buying habits, as traditional methods are not very helpful to commercial organizations in revenue growth. Businesses can adopt effective tactics for expanding sales and stepping unafraid into the competitive world by using sales predictions based on a variety of factors, including past sales.

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